

INTERTEXTUALITY AND ITS FEATURES

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Abstract: The article discusses the types of sentences in scientific style. And it is touched upon in terms of expressiveness of sentences and their behavior in the composition of the text. As well as, it examines the types of expressiveness, reflecting openness to other texts and discourses, examines its specificity in scientific discourse, highlights its main functions and analyzes the types of sentences for communicative aims and the means of their implementation.

Key words: expressiveness, affirmative, interrogative, imperative, communicative aims, scientific style.

The main elements that make up the principle of intertextuality in the text, the linguistic units are intertexts. In the process of analyzing the literature on the theory of intertextuality, we took into account that the content of the text was evaluated as the intertextuality of another fragment of the text, a proverb, an epigraph, a quote (link). A number of scientific studies have also emerged in linguistics on what intertextuality is, its types, and features, such as the theory of intertextuality.

"Intertext" is a text that is part of a certain text or a fragment of it, a term meaning parts, that is, an excerpt in context taken from another text belonging to its author, or from another text as a whole. Intertextuality is a term that directly refers to the same term as intertexts.

It is known that excerpts from the works of another writer are widely used as an intertext in the scientific text. Intertexts, in turn, acquire national-mental properties. Since the author of a literary text uses national literature, folk oral creativity based on an excerpt from a popular work of the people, as a more intertextual or national characteristic of the people. For this reason, the intertext within the text is quickly understood by the reader and begins to perceive in comparison what is said in the text. Because the text presented as an intertext will already have a place in his linguistic memory. This feature also makes it possible to study the phenomenon of intertextuality from a linguistic and cultural point of view. Also, precedent units, which are directly part of the phenomenon of intertextuality, are one of the main objects of linguoculturology. With the help of the text fragment given in this case,

the exact text itself is remembered, and this fragment, familiar to many, also acquires a renaissance character, with the help of intertext, the content of the text is again determined, its aesthetic effect on the reader is enhanced.

Scientists who have interpreted intertextuality and intertextuality as separate terms in research on the theory of intertextuality claim that it has the following properties:

- any text constantly manifests itself as a new fabric woven from old quotations (R. Barth, V. Leich, S. Grivel and etc.);
- a number of texts (intertexts) form a single text, and in general they reveal the implicit expression of the text (A. Zholkovsky, I. Smirnov, N. Fateeva);
- the content of intertexts - text, quotations (V. Rudnev);
- a component that forms the semantic structure of a work of art (S. Zolyan). This component opens the way for text interpretation.

Intertextuality is a quotation that contains an implicit content, a fragment of text, as well as the main semantically forming tool of the text, forming the intertextuality of a particular text. M. Riffater notes that intertext is a type of sociolect text that combines vocabulary and is inextricably linked to the text we read.

K. Sidorenko, on the other hand, defines the linguistic status of the intertext as being among other linguistic units. There are still two main linguistic paradigms in linguistics: the system-structural and the anthropocentric paradigms. In the first paradigm, each linguistic event is located at a certain hierarchical level, and each level has its own unit: phoneme, morpheme, lexeme, vocabulary, sentence and text. K. Sidorenko applies the term "intertexteme" to himself, asking the question of what place intertextension occupies in the system-a structural paradigm and what which unit is it represented by. In his opinion, intertextuality is considered an important segment of the structural construction of the text, providing lexical, grammatical, prosodic, compositional reinforcement of intertextual communication. In general, intertexts stand in a circular pose that unites all units of the language.

However, in the anthropocentric paradigm, this is assessed as "Man is the basis, the measure of all things." In particular, such sections of linguistics as vocabulary, phonetics, and grammar are analyzed through the prism of human thinking. Therefore, communicative processes, speech acts and other phenomena directly related to human activity come to the fore. According to this paradigm,

intertextuality is assessed as a specific textual unit bearing the cultural layers of the language.

One of the founders of the theory of intertextuality is N. Pegegro, who classifies intertexts or by abstraction. "The explicit form of intertextuality is obvious: they are set by typographic signs (italics, brackets) or semantic indicators such as the name of the remembered author, the title of the work and the hero, among others. If intertextuality is implicit, then its indicators will be ambiguous and diverse. The expressiveness noted by the scientist is understandable even without comments, but intertextuality can also be set implicitly, that is, hidden. This manifests itself mainly when integral texts are parodied, when metaphors are written, when quotations become an unmarked part of the text, when allusive titles form intertextuality. Understanding the content under the implicit form of intertextuality will depend on the reader's thinking and worldview.

Scientists also evaluate intertext from the point of view of synergetics, that is, it is a limitless, open system. In his work, the author uses this system as much as he wants. It is at this point that the question of time and intertextuality also comes into play. The author creates his work in the present (lived time), while the intertext is a product of the past tense, since it has already been created and divided as a fragment of the work of an author, as part of the Bible or as an oral work of the hulk. And in the literary text, these two tenses are combined. The main goal from here is a convincing, lively performance of the author's pose, and the level and social status of the addressee reader is also taken into account.

There are 3 basic organizing elements, these are: 1. time; 2. person; 3. text. Time is considered one of the necessary components for the manifestation of intertextuality and is a prerequisite for its occurrence.

It is known that the text describes a particular time, period. It also presents religious, mythological scientific views dating back to that time. Therefore, historical time is considered important for understanding the intertext. Because there will certainly be a discrepancy between the period in which a particular text is presented and the time when the intertext is created. And all the skill of the author of the text is manifested in the fact that he can combine these two times.

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